

Mediating Effect of Perceived Organizational Support in Role of Work-Family Conflict and Work Stress Correctional Police Officer at Temanggung Class II B Detention Center

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ABSTRACT: This study examines and analyzes work-family conflict's influence on work stress for Correctional Police Officers at Temanggung Class II B Detention Center. In addition, this study examines the mediating role of perceived organizational support on the relationship between work-family conflict and work stress. This research is quantitative and designed to test hypotheses. The data in this research is primary data taken from 40 correctional police officers with the criteria of being married. The results of this study indicate that work-family conflict has a significant positive effect on work stress. However, perceived organizational support did not significantly mediate the influence of work-family conflict on the work stress.

KEYWORDS: correctional police officers, perceived organizational support, work-family conflict, work stress.

INTRODUCTION: In some countries, the prison population has increased since the early 1900s, with more than 9 million people incarcerated in various cases (Zein, 2010). Meanwhile, the population of detainees and prisoners in Indonesia is experiencing overcapacity from the applicable occupancy standards. In November 2023, the number of residents of correctional institutions and detention centers in Indonesia reached 266,577 people, this number is greater than the occupancy capacity for only 136,980 people (sdppublik.ditjenpas.go.id). The high occupancy of correctional requires an adequate number of correctional officers. The reason is, the job description as a correctional officer is certainly not easy. On the one hand, correctional officers must carry out tasks related to the survival of correctional prisoners (WBP), or the designation for prisoners and inmates of correctional institutions, where in carrying out the guidance must prioritize human rights and minimize physical and verbal violence, also have to deal with other situations, namely overcapacity which causes several impacts including long working hours, as well as situations that arise due to the behavior of prisoners such as fights between prisoners or with officers, destruction of facilities and escape attempts, as well as other problems originating from the families of prison residents (Angkasa, 2010).

Table 1. Total Occupants and Occupancy Capacity Correctional Institutions in Indonesia in November 2023

Region	Total Occupants (Prisoners and Detainees)	Occupancy Capacity (KP)
Aceh	7969	4166
Bali	4012	1544
Banten	9728	5393
Bengkulu	2980	1792
DKI Jakarta	15289	5919
Special Region of Yogyakarta	2450	2165
Gorontalo	1098	1028
Jambi	5243	2418
West Java	24400	17036
Central Java	13319	8847
East Java	28176	13409

West Kalimantan	6750	2549
South Kalimantan	9959	4040
Central Kalimantan	4863	1967
East Kalimantan	12175	3925
Bangka Belitung Islands	2546	1311
Riau Islands	4814	2798
Lampung	8956	5130
Maluku	1679	1342
North Maluku	1230	1732
West Nusa Tenggara	3940	2494
East Nusa Tenggara	3162	2650
Papua	2931	2231
West Papua	1440	1108
South Sulawesi	8009	4405
Central Sulawesi	3761	1890
Southeast Sulawesi	3554	2441
North Sulawesi	3085	2126
West Sumatra	6382	3581
South Sumatra	15895	6400
North Sumatra	32184	13802
TOTAL	266.577	136.980

Source: sdppublik.ditjenpas.go.id (2023)

In addition to these problems, the working atmosphere of correctional officers that seems monotonous, associating with residents who are said to be difficult to socialize and problematic, working surrounded by high and closed walls, this situation can affect physical and psychological conditions. Shift-based work, work overload, risky work, tend to cause occupational stress compared to other jobs (Okoza, Imhonde and Aluede, 2010). The potential dangers of working in prisons have been studied and found to be a significant cause of stress for employees in them (Triplett, Mullings, and Scarborough, 1996). Results revealed that prison riots contributed the most to stress for correctional officers at 96%, and the least source of stress was dilapidated buildings at 50%. The results also showed that tenure had a significant main effect on the stress experienced by correctional officers while age did not have a significant main effect. This could be because critical incidents such as assaults and stabbings interfere with employees' ability to manage stress. If this is not addressed properly, secondary problems such as substance abuse, psychological and relationship problems will eventually arise.

Not finished with the conflicts experienced with prisoners, correctional officers are also close to work-family conflicts arising from the various antecedents above. Work-family conflict cannot be separated from the workers also experienced by correctional officers, who have a high workload because they are directly faced with risks. This risk can allegedly threaten the lives of the correctional officers themselves. Klinoff *et al.* (2018) indicated that there are 3 (three) dominant psychological stress experienced by correctional officers including: *work-related stress*, *institutional-related stress*, and *physco-social related stress*. These three psychological stressors are directly experienced by both male and female correctional officers. *Work-related stress* is related to problems arising from the scope of work, such as problems with suspects, detainees, and prisoners, *institutional-related stress* is related to managerial agencies, while *physco-social related stress* is related to problems arising with peers and families. Such role conflicts that may arise and affect roles in the family can be said to be work-family conflict, which for example results from long working hours (Huang *et al.*, 2004). Time spent working more than time with family is one source of stress in individuals (Soomro, Breitenecker, and Shah, 2018). Kismono's research (2011) found that there were no significant differences in family work conflict between men and women working in the Indonesian banking industry. Research conducted by Shockley *et al.* (2017) showed the same thing. Challenging lay perceptions, the results showed that men and women generally did not differ in their experience of

work-family conflict. Although there were some moderating effects of dual earner status, parental status, type of work-family conflict (i.e. time-based, tension-based, and behavior-based conflict), and when restricting the sample to men and women who have the same job.

Rhoades and Eisenberger (2002) suggest that perceived organizational support reduces workplace stressors and has the potential to combat work-related burnout, anxiety, and depression. This is in line with the research of Liu *et al.* (2013) which states that perceived organizational support is negatively associated with depressive symptoms of correctional officers in North China. Perceived organizational support such as task placement according to their capacity, organizational structure, climate created by the organization, will have a consistent relationship with job stress experienced by correctional officers. Effective interventions can reduce the stress and *burnout* felt by correctional officers (Finney *et al.*, 2013). In terms of mediation, perceived organizational support and trust significantly partially mediate the effect of overall perceived justice on self-protective behaviors (e.g., not blaming peers for work errors caused by individual stress), and work deviance, which will lead to performance (Reynolds, 2015).

Stress refers to the results experienced when a person is faced with environmental conditions that place special physical and/or psychological demands on the individual (Theorell, 1999). In the Class II B Temanggung Detention Center itself, data as of November 2023 states, there is an excess capacity of occupants with details of 130 prisoners and 34 detainees, which should be occupied with a capacity of 94 detainees because the function of the detention center according to Undang-undang no. 22 tahun 2022, concerning corrections is as a place for temporary detention of suspects, or defendants, during the process of investigation, prosecution, examination at the court session. The inmates placed in the Class II B Temanggung Detention Center come from judicial decisions due to violations of the law in Temanggung Regency, as well as transfers from other correctional institutions. As for the correctional officers in Class II B Temanggung Detention Center consists of 51 people with details of 40 people are male and 11 people are female, where the correctional officers are purely from recruitment under the Ministry of Law and Human Rights, and 3 of the 51 people come from other ministries, namely from the Ministry of Social Affairs and the Ministry of Defense. The existence of family work conflict is feared to be one of the stressors affecting the work stress of correctional officers. Research by Finney *et al.* (2013) states that work stress conditions in correctional officers can trigger high turnover rates, high absenteeism rates, low productivity and decreased levels of life satisfaction and conflict between work and family. This situation indicates that correctional officers are high-risk jobs, so individuals who occupy these jobs need to have psychological skills in overcoming situations that have the potential to cause job stress. Based on the results of an interview with the Head of the Temanggung Detention Center, Syaikoni, as of October 2023 there have been 5 correctional officers of the male gender submitting memos to work outside the Class II B Temanggung Detention Center, with the reason of wanting to be close to family, 4 of whom are married and have a long distance relationship with their spouses. Some are in different provinces and some are in 1 province but in different districts.

METHODS

This study uses a quantitative approach, by explaining the relationship between the variables studied. The data collection method used a survey with a data collection instrument in the form of a questionnaire distributed to 40 out of 51 correctional officers with married criteria. The time dimension of the research is *cross-sectional*, which is the type of data used in photographing a phenomenon at one specific time (Sekaran and Bougie, 2013). Furthermore, the data were processed using the SMART PLS 4.0 algorithm in testing the outer model, and the inner model.

DISCUSSION

The variable measurement model is measured reflectively, namely measurement based on validity and reliability (Hair *et al.*, 2021). Model evaluation consists of convergent validity with the condition that it is accepted if the *outer loading* value ≥ 0.70 , and *Average Variance Extracted (AVE)* ≥ 0.50 , discriminant validity with *Fornell and Lacker* criteria and HTMT (Heterotrait Monotrait Ratio) ≤ 0.90 , and Reliability with *Composite Reliability* ≥ 0.70 , *Cronbach's Alpha* ≥ 0.70 . If there are items with unqualified test results (marked with red items), then these items must be *dropped* or eliminated (Hair *et al.*, 2017).

Figure 1. Variable Analysis Model

In the results of this test, there are several items and indicators that must be deleted because they do not meet (including one indicator of job stress in the behavioral aspect), which then the final test results are presented in the following table.

Table 2. Outer Loading, Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability, and Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variables	Item	Indicator	Outer Loading	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability		AVE
					rho_a	rho_c	
Work-Family Conflict (X)	X2	The demands of work are high so that home affairs are not resolved	0.804	0.865	0.893	0.902	0.648
	X3	Job burnout and its impact on family life	0.764				
	X5	Feeling anxious about the arrival of new coworkers	0.740				
	X6	Stuck in a job you don't like	0.827				
	X8	High demands and orders from natural leaders of the organization	0.883				
Job Stress (Y)	Y1	Headache during work	0.896	0.933	0.937	0.950	0.790
	Y2	The impact of stress on the physical aspects of doing work	0.921				
	Y4	Emotional changes	0.898				
	Y5	A feeling of restlessness	0.914				
	Y6	Boredom level	0.812				

Perceived Organizational Support (Z)	Z1	Organizational procedural justice in employee placement	0.790	0.947	0.951	0.954	0.678
	Z2	Organizational facilities according to position	0.841				
	Z3	The organization's appreciation of any effort made	0.905				
	Z4	Paying attention to complaints	0.721				

Table 3. Discriminant Validity Fornell-Larcker Criterion

	Perceived Organizational Support	Work-family Conflict	Work Stress
Perceived Organizational Support	0.823		
Work-family Conflict	-0.680	0.805	
Work Stress	-0.623	0.710	0.889

Source: Primary data processed (2023)

Discriminant validity is a form of evaluation to ensure that variables are theoretically different and empirically proven for statistical testing (Hair *et al.*, 2019). The Fornell-Larcker criterion requires that the root AVE of the variable is greater than the correlation between variables, and the results of the discriminant validity test in this study are accepted.

Table 4. Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

Variables	Value
family work conflict <-> perceived organizational support	0.728
job stress <-> perceived organizational support	0.656
job stress <-> family work conflict	0.765

Source: primary data processed (2023)

Hair *et al.* (2019) recommends adding HTMT because this measure of discriminant validity is more sensitive or accurate in detecting discriminant validity. The recommended value is below 0.90. In table 4.9, the test results show the HTMT value below 0.90 for the variable pair. Thus, discriminant validity in this study was achieved. Inner model testing, including hypothesis testing, is carried out in three stages, the first is to check the absence of multicollinearity between variables with the inner VIF (*Variance Inflated Factor*) measure. A VIF value below 5 (or 5.00) indicates that the level of variable multicollinearity is low (Hair *et al.*, 2019).

Table 5. Inner Model Variance Inflated Factor (VIF)

	Perceived Organizational Support	Work-family Conflict	Work Stress
Perceived Organizational Support			2.09
Work-family Conflict	1.00		2.26

Source: Primary data processed (2023)

The results of table 4.10 show that the VIF value of the relationship between these variables is below 5, which means that multicollinearity between variables is low. Second, hypothesis testing is carried out by conducting a model fit test using R^2 , Q^2 , and SRMR.

Table 6. R² and Q² test

	R ²	R ² Adjusted	Q ²
Perceived Organizational Support	0.462	0.448	0.296
Work Stress	0.540	0.515	0.401

Source: Primary data processed (2023)

Based on the data in Table 4.11 shows that the *R-Square* value of the perceived organizational support variable, about 46.2% of the variance is the family work conflict variable, while the remaining 53.8% is related to external variables or factors not examined in this study. As for the stress variable, it shows that the family work conflict variable can explain 54% of its variation, while the remaining 46% is influenced by other variables or factors not examined in this study. The Q value² of organizational support variables includes a moderate prediction accuracy measure (0.29>0.25), and the Q value² of work stress variables includes a high prediction accuracy measure (0.540>0.50).

Table 7. Fit Summary Test

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.094	0.094

Source: Primary data processed (2023)

The SRMR (*Standardized Root Mean Square Residual*) value of this study is 0.094 <0.10, which indicates a *well-fitted* model. The next stage is to test the direct effect between variables by assessing the *p-value* on the significance of the relationship between variables. If the *p-value* of the test results is smaller than 0.05, then there is a significant influence between variables.

Table 8. Hypothesis Testing (Direct Effect)

Hypothesis	Path coefficient (Original Sample)	95% confidence interval path coefficient		t-statistic (≤1.96)	p-value (<0.05)
		2.5%	97.5%		
H1. Family Work Conflict □ Work Stress	0.603	0.315	0.886	4.197	0,000
H2. Job Conflict □ Perceived Organizational Support	-0.680	-0.818	-0.519	8.940	0.000
H3. Perceived Organizational Support □ Job Stress	-0.300	-0.612	0.012	1.867	0.062

Source: Primary data processed (2023)

Based on the results of hypothesis testing above, it is known as follows.

- The first hypothesis (H1) is accepted, namely that there is a positive and significant effect of family work conflict on job stress with *path coefficient* (0.603) and *p-value* (0.00 <0.05).
- The second hypothesis (H2) is accepted, namely that there is a negative and significant effect of family work conflict on perceived organizational support, with *path coefficient* (-0.680) and *p-value* (0.00 <0.05).
- The third hypothesis (H3) is rejected, namely that there is a negative but insignificant effect of perceived organizational support variables on job stress with *path coefficient* (-0.300) and *p-value* (0.06 > 0.05).
- The fourth hypothesis (H4) is rejected, namely that there is a positive but non significant effect on the mediating role of perceived organizational support on the relationship between family work conflict and job stress, with a *path coefficient* value (0.204) and *p-value* (0.08 > 0.05).

Table 9. Hypothesis Testing (Indirect Effect)

Hypothesis	Path coefficient (Original Sample)	95% confidence interval path		t-statistic (≤1.96)	p-value (<0.05)
		2.5%	97.5%		
H4. Family Work Conflict □ Perceived Organizational Support □ Job Stress	0.204	-0.009	0.451	1.727	0.084

Source: Primary data processed (2023)

RESULT

The results of the analysis show that work-family conflict directly has a positive and significant effect on the work stress of correctional officers at the Temanggung Class II B Detention Center. This supports the research of Viegas and Henriques (2021), Ariani (2020), and Setiawan (2019) that there is a positive correlation between work-family conflict and work stress. Work and family conflicts on work stress felt by correctional officers are felt by men and women because they have the same workload. Coupled with the occurrence of *over capacity* resulting in correctional officers in Class II B Temanggung Detention Center working extra. Prisoners and inmates who are made in one room and there is only a distinction between men and women make the correctional officers overwhelmed. Dual work role conflict is experienced by many women, because this conflict arises when women have to prioritize the interests of their duties and responsibilities at work rather than their family interests, and stress can arise when women have role conflicts. (Shindy *et al.*, 2023). However, based on the results of this study, it is known that the level of family work conflict felt by correctional officers of Class II B Temanggung Detention Center has a high enough influence of 60%, which is dominated by men. This contradicts some previous research listed, including research in Cinnamon and Rich (2002), which shows that men have a high level of comfort when prioritizing roles at work, while women prioritize roles in the family. In fact, 5 male correctional officers submitted transfer memos to be closer to their spouses. In addition, it is not uncommon for male and female correctional officers to have to double up from prison guards to staff treasury, logistics, inventory, public relations, availability to be *on call* if there are problems in the detention center related to prisoners (WBP) or coworkers, being the personal driver of the head of the detention center and a sudden driver when there must be official and nonofficial interests outside the detention center, and others that can cause work overtime and lead to disruption of the family domain due to work, causing conflict (Yu and Leka, 2022). Work-family conflict as a form of dual role conflict where role pressures in work and family are not aligned in some way (Breyer & Bluemke, 2016) when a husband considers there is equality and willingness to share tasks from both parties, or in other words, there is a husband's willingness to share roles with his wife in work and household matters (Kismono, 2011). Thus, when a husband's role in the family begins to be disrupted due to intervention from the work domain, he experiences work-family conflict. Based on the results of this study, it is known that the high organizational support perceived by correctional officers of Class II B Temanggung Detention Center is able to reduce family work conflict, with a direct effect of 68%. This supports Lingard and Francis (2006) research regarding several things that can be done to reduce work-family conflict is support from superiors, coworkers, and organizations so that employees are able to balance roles and responsibilities at work and in the family. The organization is considered a place to work that can also help balance these roles and responsibilities by providing support and accommodating employee interests even outside the organization. In this case, the organization should have a proactive approach to implementing some work-life balancing practices for its members in order to create perceived organizational support (Gómez and Marti, 2004). In addition, another study mentioned that, creating a flexible structure to make environmental changes, and contributing to increasing individual life satisfaction so that it will reduce conflict (Ahn, 2005). The results of the analysis show that perceived organizational support directly has a negative but insignificant effect on the job stress of correctional officers in Class II B Temanggung Detention Center. This means that the effect of organizational support is not meaningful because it may be so small, and there needs to be consideration of other factors that may affect the significance of the effect of perceived organizational support on job stress. The results of this study reject the results of previous studies which state that high levels of perceived organizational support and good organizational culture will reduce levels of job stress (Hafidhah and Martono, 2019) and Purnama and Wulandari (2023) which state that, when perceived organizational support is low, job stress will increase and vice versa. There

may be some external factors beyond perceived organizational support that can cause an increase or decrease in stress, as a result of the correctional institution environment itself such as overcapacity, overcrowded conditions in correctional institutions, lack of privacy, lack of facilities and health care, and isolation from family (Bedaso, Kediro, Yeneabat., 2018). In the page *ditjenpas.go.id.*, the term correctional is standardized as a substitute for imprisonment (imprisonment), which is a change from the concept of retaliation and deterrence to the restoration of the life and life functions of correctional prisoners (WBP). The correctional system is based on social reintegration from changes in arbitrary treatment of lawbreakers, to changes that prioritize the benefits of post-prison sentences and human rights without exception, both men and women in 1 (one) correctional institution, which becomes an obstacle for correctional officers when taking action against prisoners of the opposite sex (Jenne and Kersting, 1996). The occurrence of *over capacity with* an unbalanced ratio of correctional officers to prisoners, both in terms of number and gender, as well as direct exposure to suspects/defendants, or prisoners is required to be professional regardless of the criminal acts committed by prisoners (WBP) which results in increased stress (Walters, 2022). The results of the analysis show that perceived organizational support has an influence but is not significant in mediating the effect of work-family conflict on the work stress of correctional officers at Class II B Temanggung Detention Center. That is, the data statistically did not succeed in proving a meaningful influence between variables. This study rejects the research of Lingard and Francis (2006) when an organizational support is perceived as a matter of how far the employee feels the company or organization contributes and cares about his welfare will reduce negative effects such as work stress due to role conflict that occurs significantly. Although in order for an organization to obtain optimal perceived organizational support from employees, the organization must at least provide fair treatment for its employees (Dewa and Salendu, 2018). Apparently, perceived organizational support is not meaningful enough for correctional officers of Class II B Temanggung Detention Center in mediating the effect of work-family conflict on experienced work stress, it is just that work conflict can be suppressed when perceived organizational support functions as a mediator, and is able to reduce symptoms that lead as one indication of stress (Hao *et al.*, 2016).

CONCLUSION

Work family conflict has a positive and significant effect on the work stress of correctional officers of Class II B Temanggung Detention Center, but the mediating role of perceived organizational support is not significant mediating the relationship between the two variables. There are several other factors that should be considered in the choice of mediation.

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